

Synthesis and spectroscopic (^1H , ^{13}C , ^{51}V NMR) and FT-IR investigation of some vanadium(V) Schiff base complexes

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Manuscript received 20 December 2016, revised 17 January 2017, accepted 27 January 2017

Abstract : Reactions of vanadium(V) oxytrichloride (VOCl_3) with various Schiff bases in different molar ratios (1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3) afforded complexes of the type $[\text{VOCl}_{3-n}(\text{sb})_n]$ [where $n = 1-3$; sb = Schiff bases; salicylidine-1-aminobenzene (sabH) and salicylidine-4-methyl-1-aminobenzene (p-smabH)]. These solid, colored complexes have been characterized by elemental analysis, FT-IR, NMR and mass studies. On the basis of these studies a plausible structure have been proposed tentatively for these complexes.

Keywords : Vanadium(V) oxytrichloride, Schiff base, IR, ^{51}V NMR, mass studies.

Introduction

During the recent past, there has been interesting development in the chemistry of vanadium(V) and niobium(V) derivatives containing Schiff bases, some vanadium complexes shows promising anticancer¹ activity and helpful in enhancing insulin² action in biological systems. Therefore, vanadium compounds in medicine have focused their *in vitro* and *in vivo* activity in the treatment of insulin deficiency³. Furthermore, vanadium complexes play an important role in a variety of biochemical processes, such as haloperoxidation⁴⁻⁸, nitrogen fixation^{9,10}, phosphorylation¹¹, glycogen metabolism¹²⁻¹⁴, insulin mimicking¹⁵⁻¹⁸ and in anti-parasitic agents¹⁹. Schiff base complexes of vanadium showed important catalytic activity in

epoxidation²⁰, oxidation²⁰⁻²³, epoxidation of alkenes^{24,25}, liquid phase hydroxylation of phenol²⁶ etc. Taking above facts in view, we report herein the synthesis and physico-chemical characterization of oxovanadium(V) complexes containing bidentate Schiff bases.

Results and discussion

Vanadium(V) complexes (**1-6**) have been synthesized by the interactions of VOCl_3 with salicylidine-1-aminobenzene (sabH) and salicylidine-4-methyl-1-aminobenzene (p-smabH) in different molar ratios (1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3) in C_6H_6 -EtOH. Plausible structure of complexes shown in Scheme 1. All these solid, colored complexes are soluble in CHCl_3 , DMSO, DMF etc. Some physical properties of these complexes are listed in Table 1.

Scheme 1. General structure of oxovanadium(V) complexes **1-6**.

Table 1. Physical state and analytical details of oxovanadium(V) complexes **1-6**

Sl. No.	Product (Empirical formula)	Yield (%)	NaCl (g) Found (Calcd.)	Colour and state	M.p. (°C)	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)				
						C	H	N	Cl	V
1.	$[(\mu\text{-Cl})_2\text{V}_2\text{O}_2(\text{Cl})_2(\text{p-smab})_2]$ 1	65	0.276 (0.254)	Dark green solid	258	48.01 (48.30)	3.19 (3.47)	3.89 (4.02)	20.16 (20.37)	13.82 (14.03)
2.	$[(\text{Cl})\text{VO}(\text{p-smab})_2]$ 2	72	0.767 (0.761)	Olive solid	245	64.04 (64.31)	4.48 (4.62)	5.12 (5.35)	6.61 (6.78)	9.56 (9.74)
3.	$[\text{VO}(\text{p-smab})_3]$ 3	67	0.572 (0.578)	Olive solid	220	72.06 (72.30)	5.03 (5.19)	5.93 (6.02)	–	7.04 (7.30)
4.	$[(\mu\text{-Cl})_2\text{V}_2\text{O}_2(\text{Cl})_2(\text{sab})_2]$ 4	69	0.334 (0.302)	Dark green solid	255	46.61 (46.74)	2.86 (3.01)	3.89 (4.92)	21.03 (21.25)	15.00 (15.24)
5.	$[(\text{Cl})\text{VO}(\text{sab})_2]$ 5	73	0.381 (0.356)	Dark green solid	230	63.90 (63.10)	3.85 (4.07)	5.52 (5.66)	6.97 (7.16)	9.95 (10.29)
6.	$[\text{VO}(\text{sab})_3]$ 6	70	0.708 (0.680)	Dark green solid	219	71.27 (71.45)	4.34 (4.60)	6.28 (6.40)	–	7.58 (7.77)

Infrared spectral studies :

The characteristic infrared frequencies of vanadium(V) complexes are summarized in Table 2. The Schiff bases; salicylidine-1-aminobenzene (sabH) and salicylidine-4-methyl-1-aminobenzene (p-smabH) showed strong and broad absorption band²⁷ at 3426 and 3458 cm^{-1} , respectively due to hydrogen bonded OH stretching vibration. This band was absent in the complexes, indicating the participation of phenolic oxygen in the formation of vanadium-oxygen bond. The strong intensity band at 1268–1262 cm^{-1} in the parent Schiff bases²⁷ due to the $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$, was shifted towards higher frequency in the region (1342–1284) cm^{-1} indicating the bonding through phenolic oxygen of the Schiff base to vanadium atom. The involvement of phenolic oxygen in bonding was further supported by the appearance of new bands²² in the region 555–540 cm^{-1} due to $\nu_{\text{V-O}}$. Schiff base ligands showed strong and sharp band in the region 1635–1616 cm^{-1} due to the $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ stretching vibration. This band was shifted towards lower frequency²³ in vanadium complexes indi-

cating involvement of azomethine nitrogen atom in bonding. This fact was further evident by the appearance of new absorption bands in the region 480–455 cm^{-1} , assignable to $\nu_{\text{V-N}}$. In the IR spectra of the oxovanadium(V) complexes, the oxo nature of the complex is confirmed by the appearance of V=O stretching bands in the range²² 958–945 cm^{-1} . Complexes **1** and **4** exhibit band in the region 270–258 cm^{-1} have been assigned to the bridging $\nu_{\text{V-Cl}}$ vibration and showing the dimeric nature of these complexes **1** and **4**.

¹H NMR spectral studies :

In the ¹H NMR spectra of salicylidine-1-aminobenzene (sabH) and salicylidine-4-methyl-1-aminobenzene (p-smabH) Schiff bases²⁷, sharp resonance band was observed at 12.40 and 12.76 ppm, respectively, which was found to be absent in the complexes, showing the deprotonation of phenolic proton due to metallation reaction. The azomethine hydrogen signal observed in the Schiff bases²⁷ in the region 8.40–8.23 ppm which was shifted downfield and observed in the region 8.87–8.73

Table 2. IR spectral data (cm^{-1}) of oxovanadium(V) complexes **1-6** containing Schiff bases

Sr. No.	Complexes	$\nu_{\text{C=N}}$	$\nu_{\text{C-O}}$	$\nu_{\text{V=O}}$	$\nu_{\text{V-O}}$	$\nu_{\text{V-N}}$	$\nu_{(\text{V-Cl})\text{ter}}$	$\nu_{(\text{V-Cl})\text{brid}}$
1.	$[(\mu\text{-Cl})_2\text{V}_2\text{O}_2(\text{Cl})_2(\text{p-smab})_2]$ 1	1602	1342	905	543	453	357	270
2.	$[(\text{Cl})\text{VO}(\text{p-smab})_2]$ 2	1601	1320	909	540	455	354	–
3.	$[\text{VO}(\text{p-smab})_3]$ 3	1605	1284	911	555	457	–	–
4.	$[(\mu\text{-Cl})_2\text{V}_2\text{O}_2(\text{Cl})_2(\text{sab})_2]$ 4	1606	1321	892	540	464	348	258
5.	$[(\text{Cl})\text{VO}(\text{sab})_2]$ 5	1599	1317	905	545	461	352	–
6.	$[\text{VO}(\text{sab})_3]$ 6	1597	1315	903	547	451	–	–

ppm for their corresponding vanadium(V) complexes. Such downfield shifting of azomethine hydrogen is indicative of the involvement of azomethine nitrogen to vanadium atom²² in complex formation. Important ^1H NMR data are given in Table 3. A representative ^1H NMR spectrum of complex **4** is given as Fig. 1.

^{13}C NMR spectral studies :

Selected ^{13}C NMR values are shown in Table 3. In the parent Schiff bases signal due to azomethine carbon is observed 156.5–159.8 ppm region, whereas these signals are observed 163.87–158.67 ppm region in the vanadium complexes. Such deshielding is characteristic of coordination²¹ of the azomethine nitrogen to vanadium(V) in the complexes. The signal appearing 151.1–150.8 ppm region in the spectra of Schiff bases due to phenolic carbon²¹ shifted to 157.94–154.62 ppm region in the vanadium(V) complexes. Such downfield shifts²¹ are consistent with the formation of vanadium-oxygen bond. These results support the bidentate coordinating behavior of Schiff bases used in the present course of investigation. A representative ^{13}C NMR spectrum of complex **4** is given as Fig. 2.

^{51}V NMR spectral studies :

^{51}V NMR spectroscopy is an excellent tool to characterize the vanadium(V) complexes, because these complexes exhibit very unusual ^{51}V shielding conditions. The ^{51}V -chemical shift values for normal penta- to hepta-co-

ordinated vanadium complexes have been reported²² between 450–600 ppm.

^{51}V NMR spectra of oxovanadium(V) complexes **1** and **4** showed signal at –509 ppm and –510 ppm region respectively, suggesting the oxovanadium(V) complexes in six coordinate environment. A representative ^{51}V NMR spectrum of complex **4** is given as Fig. 3.

Mass spectral studies :

Mass spectra of complexes $[(\mu\text{-Cl})_2\text{V}_2\text{O}_2(\text{Cl})_2(\text{p-smab})_2]$ **1** (Fig. 4), $[(\text{Cl})\text{VO}(\text{p-smab})_2]$ **2** (Fig. S1) and $[\text{OV}(\text{p-smab})_3]$ **3** (Fig. S2) showed molecular ion peak at m/z 696.36 $[(\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{24}\text{Cl}_4\text{N}_2\text{O}_4\text{V}_2)]$; (Calcd. mass = 693.93), 523.27 $[(\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{ClV})]$; (Calcd. mass = 522.881) and m/z 692.35 $[(\text{C}_{42}\text{H}_{36}\text{N}_3\text{O}_4\text{V})]$; (Calcd. mass = 697.69), respectively which is indicative for dimeric nature of complex **1** and monomeric nature of complexes **2** and **3**. Observed isotopic distribution for molecular ion peak at m/z 505.27 and peak at m/z 488.16 for complexes **2** shown in Fig. S3 and for complexes **3** observed isotopic distribution for molecular ion peak at m/z 691.31 shown in Fig. S4. Calculated isotopic distribution for molecular ion peak at m/z 522.88 and peak at m/z 508.07 for complexes **2** are shown in Fig. S5, whereas, calculated isotopic distribution for molecular ion peak at m/z 697.21 for complex **3** shown in Fig. S6; whereas, different fragmentation patterns^{29,30} with m/z for the corresponding com-

Table 3. ^1H NMR and ^{13}C NMR data (ppm) for oxovanadium(V) complexes **1-6**

Sr. No.	Complexes	^1H NMR			^{13}C NMR			
		HC=N	Ar-H	Ar-CH ₃	C=N (azomethine)	C=O (phenolic)	Ar-C	Ar-CH ₃
1.	$[(\mu\text{-Cl})_2\text{V}_2\text{O}_2(\text{Cl})_2(\text{p-smab})_2]$ 1	8.78 (1H, s)	6.54–7.54 (16H, m)	2.20 (6H, s)	158.67 (2C, s)	156.45 (2C, s)	144.76–116.67 (24C, s)	20.42 (2C, s)
2.	$[(\text{Cl})\text{VO}(\text{p-smab})_2]$ 2	8.87 (2H, s)	6.57–7.7.67 (16H, m)	2.25 (6H, s)	161.91 (2C, s)	155.23 (2C, s)	145.37–118.63 (24C, s)	18.43 (2C, s)
3.	$[\text{VO}(\text{p-smab})_3]$ 3	8.82 (3H, s)	6.49–7.56 (24H, m)	2.18 (9H, s)	163.87 (3C, s)	157.94 (3C, s)	143.32–119.20 (36C, s)	20.20 (3C, s)
4.	$[(\mu\text{-Cl})_2\text{V}_2\text{O}_2(\text{Cl})_2(\text{sab})_2]$ 4	8.86 (1H, s)	6.14–7.34 (16H, m)		159.27 (2C, s)	154.81 (2C, s)	143.43–117.21 (24C, s)	
5.	$[(\text{Cl})\text{VO}(\text{sab})_2]$ 5	8.73 (2H, s)	6.17–7.7.26 (16H, m)		162.30 (2C, s)	155.82 (2C, s)	145.97–118.49 (24C, s)	
6.	$[\text{VO}(\text{sab})_3]$ 6	8.77 (3H, s)	6.68–7.15 (24H, m)		161.53 (3C, s)	154.62 (3C, s)	144.13–119.93 (36C, s)	

plexes are shown in Schemes 2, S1 and S2, respectively. Complex 1 shows important peaks at m/z 613.16, 569.37, 525.33, 456.33, 419.20, 352.21, 314.26, 274.35, 264.39, 222.58, 199.76, 145.33 and 96.19 due to the formation of the $\bullet\text{CH}_3$, $\bullet\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$, $\bullet\text{Cl}$, $\bullet\text{O}$ and HCN radicals and small molecule. Complex 2 shows prominent peaks at m/z 574.29, 512.26, 485.22, 446.21, 445.20, 441.25, 399.20, 369.21, 331.29, 291.27, 225.62, 213.66, 195.77 and 137.44 due to the formation of the $\bullet\text{CH}_3$, $\bullet\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{N}$, $\bullet\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{O}$,

$\bullet\text{C}_7\text{H}_7$, HCN, $\bullet\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$, $\bullet\text{O}$, $\bullet\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$ and $\bullet\text{VO}$ radicals. The spectrum of complex 3 exhibits various peaks at m/z 446.20, 445.20, 446.20, 436.22, 421.23, 355.22, 354.22, 316.30, 250.47, 213.66, 195.77 and 138.41 due to the formation of various radicals $\bullet\text{CH}_3$, $\bullet\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$, $\bullet\text{C}_7\text{H}_7\text{N}$, HCN, $\bullet\text{Cl}$, $\bullet\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{O}$ and $\bullet\text{C}_6\text{H}_7$.

Experimental

Material and methods :

Fig. 1. ^1H NMR spectrum of complex 4.

Fig. 2. ^{13}C NMR spectrum of complex 4.

Fig. 3. ^{51}V NMR spectrum of complex 4.

Fig. 4. LC-MS spectrum of complex $[(\mu\text{-Cl})_2\text{V}_2\text{O}_2(\text{Cl})_2(\text{p-sab})_2]$ **1**.

Vanadium(v) oxytrichloride (Sigma Aldrich, 99%) were used as received without further purification. Salicylaldehyde, *p*-toluidine and aniline (Loba) were used without purification. Analytical grade (Merck, India) solvents were made anhydrous and purified by the literature methods²⁸.

Infrared spectra ($400\text{--}4000\text{ cm}^{-1}$) were recorded on 100 FTIR/RZX Perkin-Elmer FT-IR spectrophotometer and Nicole Instrument MAGMA 550 were used to record spectra from $600\text{ to }50\text{ cm}^{-1}$. NMR : ^1H (300.40 MHz, DMSO- d_6 , TMS), ^{13}C (75.45 MHz, DMSO- d_6 , TMS) and ^{51}V (111.95 MHz, DMSO- d_6 , VOCl_3) were recorded on Bruker-Avance (II) 400 NMR. Perkin-Elmer 2400 analyzer was used for elemental analysis. Mass spectra of compounds were recorded on WATERS, Q-TOF MICROMASS (LC-MS) in acetonitrile.

Synthesis of Schiff bases :

Salicylidine-4-methyl-1-amino benzene (p-sabH) : An ethanolic solution ($\sim 30\text{ cm}^3$) of salicylaldehyde (5.73 g, 47.0 mmol) was added to ethanolic solution of *p*-toluidine (5.028 g, 47.0 mmol) with constant stirring and refluxed

for $\sim 6\text{ h}$ to give bright yellow solution which on cooling at room temperature afforded yellow crystals. It was recrystallized from ethanol to get analytically pure bright yellow crystals. m.p. : $60\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Yield : 85%; Anal. Found : C, 79.43; H, 6.03; N, 6.45%. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{13}\text{NO}$: C, 79.59; H, 6.20; N, 6.63%.

Salicylidine-1-amino benzene (sabH) : An equimolar amount of salicylaldehyde (5.73 g, 47 mmol) and aminobenzene (4.37 g, 47 mmol) in ethanol ($\sim 30\text{ cm}^3$) was refluxed for $\sim 4\text{ h}$ during which the solution turned yellow. The excess of mixture of solvent was removed by distillation to obtain yellow solid. It was further recrystallized from ethanol and dried under reduced pressure to get yellow crystal. m.p. : $52\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Yield : 75%; Anal. Found : C, 78.95; H, 5.49; N, 6.93%. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{11}\text{NO}$: C, 79.16; H, 5.62; N, 7.10%.

Synthesis of the complexes :

Similar procedure was used for the preparation of the complexes (**1-6**), of the type $[\text{VOCl}_{3-n}(\text{sb})_n]$ therefore for

Scheme 2. Fragmentation pattern of complex $[(\mu\text{-Cl})_2\text{V}_2\text{O}_2(\text{Cl})_2(\text{p-smab})_2]$ 1.

the sake of brevity general preparative details are given below :

To benzene (~ 30 ml) solution of VOCl_3 a EtOH (~ 30 ml) solution of an appropriate sodium salt of Schiff base (prepared by dissolving equimolar amount of sodium metal and a Schiff base (sbH) in EtOH (~ 30 ml)] was added dropwise in different molar ratios (1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3) with constant stirring. The reaction mixture was allowed to reflux for 6 h. The precipitated NaCl was removed by filtration. The solvent was removed by distillation. The solid products were dried under reduced pressure and recrystallized from mixture of dichloromethane-hexane.

Acknowledgement

Authors are thankful to Director, SAIF, Chandigarh for spectral data. Special thanks to Dr. K. N. Uttam, Physics Department, University of Allahabad for FT-IR data and SAIF, IIT Bombay for FAR IR studies.

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